

Synthesis and photopolymerization of 2-(1H-imidazol-1-yl)-1-(naphthalen-2-yl) ethan-1-one

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Abstract

Photo curing technology, as an environment-friendly technology, has been widely applied to chemical, machinery, electronics, light industry, communications, and other industries. The most important component of photo curing systems is photoinitiator, which can absorb UV light and therefore generate active species, leading to the photopolymerization of unsaturated monomers or resins. Imidazoles are a very important class of nitrogen-containing heterocyclic compounds. They have diverse applications in a wide range of organic synthesis fields, including agriculture, medicine, polymers, and various industries. In the presented study, imidazole based 2-(1H-imidazol-1-yl)-1-(naphthalen-2-yl) ethan-1-one (IPY) was synthesized and characterized as a novel acetonaphthone derivative photoinitiator. The effect of IPY concentration and the addition of N-methyl diethanolamine (MDEA) as a co-initiator on the polymerization of methyl methacrylate (MMA) was investigated.

Keywords: Photopolymerization, photoinitiator, acetonaphthone, absorption spectrum, imidazole.

1. INTRODUCTION

Photoinitiated polymerization is of increasing importance in industrial and academic studies, combining many economic and ecological prospects. Photopolymerization is an important industrial process frequently used in many fields such as inks, coatings, adhesives, contact lenses, varnishes, microelectronics, micro lithography, biomaterials, etc. due to its various advantages. In addition, photo curable systems are used in the production of hard and abrasion resistant materials such as dental fillers, sealants, composite membranes, fibers and reinforced plastics [1-3]. Photopolymerization process provides advantages such as high polymerization rate at room temperature, low energy consumption, polymerization in solvent free environment, control of the surface area and application time. Photopolymerization can be carried out at lower temperatures than thermal polymerization. For instance, methods have been developed for coating the surface of wood, paper, metal and plastic materials and photochemically hardening these coatings, which provide important areas of use [4-6].

The most important component of the photopolymerization process is the photoinitiators that absorb electromagnetic radiation at the appropriate wavelength and produce initiator radicals. The reactive species formed as a result of the absorption of light at a suitable wavelength of the photoinitiator enable the polymerization of monofunctional monomers and the conversion of multifunctional monomers into cross-linked structures [7-11]. Photoinitiators, especially those containing free radicals and relating systems, are mainly classified into two categories according to their optical behavior: Type I photoinitiators undergo bond cleavage upon light absorption to produce initiating radicals. Type II photoinitiators require a co-initiator and form initiator species as a result of electron and hydrogen transfer following photoexcitation. Another type of one component type II

photoinitiators produce initiator radicals by intramolecular or intermolecular hydrogen transfer without the need for a co-initiator [12-15].

Type II photoinitiators are considered advantageous due to their ability to operate under low-energy light sources compared to Type I systems. Typically, the photochemical bond cleavage of photoinitiators requires a relatively high energy input, often necessitating the use of high-energy light sources. In contrast, Type II photoinitiators possess absorption characteristics at longer wavelengths, enabling them to utilize light within the visible region. Owing to this property, they are often regarded as components of “green” technology and are preferred in various applications. This feature allows the use of low-energy illumination, thereby reducing operational costs and facilitating photopolymerization in systems sensitive to high-energy radiation, such as those used in biological and medical contexts [16-20]. Imidazole derivatives are well recognized as pharmaceutical intermediates and curing agents for epoxy resins. However, to the best of our knowledge, studies investigating the use of imidazole as a co-initiator in Type II photoinitiator systems have been scarcely reported [21-22].

Recently acetonaphthone derivatives are synthesized and characterized for the polymerization of MMA monomer [23-27]. In this study, a novel imidazole based acetonaphthone derivative 2-(1H-imidazol-1-yl)-1-(naphthalen-2-yl) ethan-1-one (IPY) was synthesized and characterized as a photoinitiator for the polymerization of methyl methacrylate monomer.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Materials

2-Bromo-2'-acetylnaphthalene (99%), imidazole (99%), N-methyl diethanolamine (MDEA, 99%), potassium carbonate (K_2CO_3 , 99%), and N, N-dimethylformamide (DMF, 99%) were

purchased from Sigma-Aldrich and used without further purification. Dichloromethane (DCM, 99.9%) was obtained from Merck and used as received. Methyl methacrylate (MMA, 99%) was supplied by Alfa Aesar purified by passage through an alumina column to remove the inhibitor, and subsequently dried over calcium chloride (CaCl_2).

2.2. Methods

Infrared spectra were measured using a Nicolet 6700 FT-IR spectrophotometer. Photopolymerization experiments were performed using an 8-watt photoreactor consisting of 12 UV lamps.

2.3. Synthesis of IPY

0.22 g imidazole (1.0 mmol) was dissolved in 0.5 mL dry DMF, transferred to a two-neck flask, and heated. 0.41 g (1.2 mmol) K_2CO_3 was added. The reaction was stirred at room temperature for 1 hour. 0.75 g (1.2 mmol) of 2-bromo-2'-acetylnaphthalene was dissolved in 1.5 ml of dry DMF and slowly added to the reaction. The progress of the reaction was monitored by thin-layer chromatography and was observed to be complete within 24 hours under an N_2 atmosphere. The reaction mixture was poured into a saturated ice-salt water solution filtered, and the product (Fig. 2.1) was obtained by drying.

Fig. 2.1. Structure of IPY.

FTIR (ATR): $\nu = 3390$ (aromatic C-H), 2960 (aliphatic C-H), 1690 (C=O), 1650 (C=N), 1500 (aromatic C=C), 1200 (C-N) cm^{-1} .

2.4. Photoinitiated Polymerization

Solutions of IPY photoinitiator of 2.5×10^{-3} and 5×10^{-3} molar concentrations were prepared in 9 molar MMA monomer. Samples were placed in Pyrex tubes (i.d. = 9 mm) and irradiated in a photoreactor under air and N_2 atmosphere. The resulting polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA) was precipitated in excess methyl alcohol and dried in a vacuum oven. Other photopolymerization processes were carried out by using N-methyl diethanolamine (MDEA) as a co-initiator. Polymerization rates (R_p) and conversion percentages (conv.%) were obtained gravimetrically by using equations (1) and (2).

$$\text{Conv. (\%)} = \frac{W}{m \times 100} \quad (1)$$

w: Polymer weight (g)

m: Monomer weight (g)

$$R_p = \frac{W \times 1000}{M \times V \times t} \quad (2)$$

M: Molar mass of monomer (g)

w: Polymer weight (g)

V: Solution volume (ml)

t: Polymerization duration (min.)

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Absorption Spectrum of IPY

The UV-absorption spectrum of IPY was measured in dichloromethane and the molar absorption coefficient was found to be $2154 \text{ L} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1} \cdot \text{cm}^{-1}$ at 336 nm (Figure 2.2). The molar

absorption coefficient of IPY is consistent with other synthesized acetone naphthone derivatives [23-27].

Figure 2.2. Absorption spectrum of IPY [5.6×10^{-4} M].

3.2. Photoinitiated Polymerization of MMA in the Presence of IPY

The photopolymerization of MMA monomer at different concentrations of IPY was carried out for 60 minutes. A photoreactor equipped with 12 UV lamps was used as the light source and the results are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Photoinitiated Bulk Polymerization of MMA with IPY.

Run ^a	IPY (M)	MDEA (M)	Conv. (%)	Rp x 10 ⁵ (mol/mL.min)
1	2.5x10 ⁻³	-	-	-
2	2.5x10 ⁻³	-	0.4 ^b	2
3	2.5x10 ⁻³	0.34	8.6	44.5
4	2.5x10 ⁻³	0.34	10.2 ^b	53.2
5	5x10 ⁻³	-	-	-
6	5x10 ⁻³	-	0.4 ^b	2
7	5x10 ⁻³	0.34	5.4	14
8	5x10 ⁻³	0.34	13.6 ^b	35.5

^a [MMA] = 9 M, ^b Under N₂ atm.

When examining the polymerization results, no polymer formation was observed in the air environment for both concentrations. In the nitrogen atmosphere, low conversion percentages and rates are determined (2.5x10⁻³, 5x10⁻³ M; conversion: 0.4%). To investigate the optimum photoinitiator concentration, two different concentrations of photoinitiator were used for polymerization. According to the polymerization results, it was observed that the conversion percentage and rate (Rp) values increased as the IPY concentration increased. When MDEA was added to the formulations, the conversion percentage values increased. When tertiary amines were added to the formulations, the oxygen in the environment decreased and initiator particles formed. For this purpose, the photopolymerization of samples containing NMDEA was carried out under a nitrogen atmosphere. According to the polymerization results, NMDEA reacts with oxygen and reduces the retarding effect of oxygen.

CONCLUSION

A novel acetonaphthone-based photoinitiator, 2-(1H-imidazol-1-yl)-1-(naphthalen-2-yl) ethan-1-one (IPY), was successfully synthesized and thoroughly characterized. The photoinitiated polymerization behavior of IPY was evaluated in the presence of MMA under irradiation. The initiator exhibited a broad absorption band in the UV–visible region, with a maximum absorption peak observed at 336 nm. The polymerization experiments, together with the absorption spectra of the obtained PMMA, confirmed that IPY efficiently initiates the polymerization of MMA in the absence of a co-initiator under a nitrogen atmosphere. These findings suggest that the polymerization proceeds via a Norrish type I cleavage mechanism. Thus, it is thought that IPY, which is based on imidazole in its acetonaphthone structure, can be used as an effective photoinitiator in the polymerization of methyl methacrylate.

Authors contribution

SK.D.– conceptualization, investigation, data curation, writing original draft, funding acquisition, editing; A.O. – formal analysis.

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